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dialogue
begin**

D4.1 JUST TRANSITION CONCEPT REVIEW AND ADAPTATION FOR FIRELOGUE

Project: **Cross-sector dialogue for Wildfire Risk Management**

Acronym: **Firelogue**

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
AFOLU	Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use
ALFA	Arnhem Land Fire Abatement
CC	Climate Change
CMCC	Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici
CP	Civil Protection
CTFC	Forest Science and Technology Centre of Catalonia
D	Distributional
DRM	Disaster Risk Management
DRR	Disaster Risk Reduction
EC	European Commission
EN	Environmental/Ecology
EU	European Union
EWE	Extreme Wildfire Events
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations
FEMA	Federal Emergency Management Agency
FhG	Fraunhofer Gesellschaft für Angewandte Forschung e.V.
GHG	Greenhouse Gas Emissions
HEV	Hazard, Exposure, Vulnerability
IFM	Integrated Fire Management
ILO	International Labour Organisation
IN	Infrastructures
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IUFRO	International Union of Forest Research Organizations
IIASA	International Institute of Applied System Analysis
INESTEC	Instituto de Engenharia de Sistemas e Computadores, Tecnologia e Ciência
IS	Insurances
JT	Just Transition
KEMEA	Centre for Security Studies
LUC	Land Use Changes
NBSs	Nature-Based Solutions
NOA	National Observatory of Athens
P	Procedural
R	Restorative
RES	Renewable Energy Source
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SO	Societal
TIEMS	The International Emergency Management Society
UN	United Nations
UNDRR	United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction
UNEP	United Nations Environmental Program
VOST	Voluntary Operations Support Teams
VOST PT	Virtual Operations Support Team Portugal

Executive Summary

This document reviews different approaches to Just Transition in terms of ambition and justice dimensions considered and their implications for stakeholder inclusion and relevance to wildfire risk management. Based on this review, it identifies relevant conceptual dimensions and tailors the concept for the dialogue workshops and their wildfire risk management focus foreseen in Firelogue project, aimed at suggesting a Firelogue – Just Transition approach. Contents are developed in four sections: Chapter 1 introduces Just Transition concept, highlighting the relevance and challenges for its application to disaster risk management context. Chapter 2 approaches multi-aspects involved within integrated risk management and the trade-offs along the risk creation and reduction process in terms of stakeholders' engagement, contributions and responsibilities for the particular case of wildfires. Chapter 3 describes main impacts of climate change to wildfire risk management. Finally, Chapter 4 discusses interlinkages between Just Transition and wildfire risk management. On one hand, how climate change mitigation actions and related Just Transition may influence wildfire risk management and vice-versa is presented. Subsequently, Just Transition aspects within wildfire risk management are detailed and structured on risk management phases and cross-sectoral dimensions of risk management, aimed at guiding the dialogues across the working groups. Lastly, a Chapter of conclusions summarizes main findings. During the drafting of the outcome document, working groups and thematic strands leaders were consulted and all members of Firelogue consortium had the chance to participate in an online consultation.

1. Introduction and definition of Just Transition concept

Just Transition (JT) and Wildfire Risk Management (WFRM) have so far been addressed by different communities and with different foci. WFRM focussed on the reduction of wildfire risk through a diversity of approaches ranging from preventive activities such as informative campaigns or landscape management to response operations and recovery or restorative strategies. While more inclusive approaches consider a range of stakeholders, the real *integration* of measures remains a challenge. JT discussions and approaches have been developed since the 1980s with a focus on climate mitigation and on balancing emission reduction activities by countermeasures. Focusing on the effect of measures from a justice perspective, JT thereby facilitated the outcome-oriented view of measures taken and related them to compensation discussions. The below sections will detail the origin and main aspects of both concepts.

Overall, Firelogue presupposes that integrating JT to WFRM could facilitate an outcome-oriented discussion about desired futures, broaden the view including downsides of measures and help to grasp the interests of different stakeholder groups. In addition, the facilitation of multi-stakeholder dialogues making use of JT could potentially also allow to better understand the compensation options in complex decision-making contexts. Firelogue thereby sets conceptual grounds since the application of JT to wider contexts including disaster risk management (DRM) more generally has so far vastly been overlooked.

Just Transition origins

The term Just Transition was first coined by the trade union movement in the 1980s (Abraham, 2017). It was born out of the United States' labour movement focusing on job restoration from the replacement of coal mining jobs with those situated in the low carbon economy (Thomas, 2021). Over the past decades, it became a key concept in promoting green and decent jobs as a necessary component of the transition away from fossil fuels (Abraham, 2017). Specifically, since the adoption of the Paris Agreement in 2015, there has been a growing focus on JT to help achieve the economic and social changes necessary for sustainable development, while protecting workers and communities, and ensuring a more socially equitable distribution of benefits and risks of climate change.

With its focus on labour aspects of fossil fuel phase out, it has been widely applied by trade unions that developed a number of toolboxes and handbooks related to JT. These include for example the International Labour Organisation's (ILO) *Guidelines for a just transition towards environmentally sustainable economies and societies for all* (2015), with a focus on the "**decent work agenda**," consisting of social dialogue, social protection, rights at work, and employment, the World Bank's *Managing Coal Mine Closure: Achieving a Just Transition for All* (2018) or the International Council on Mining and Metals' (*Integrated Mine Closure - Good Practice Guide* (2019) guidelines).

Last but not least, justice considerations also play a key role in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), adopted in 2015 by the United Nations (UN), understanding JT such as an "*economy-wide process that produces the plans, policies, and investments that build resilient economies and*

communities” including emissions reductions, resilience to climate risks and, the creation of decent work (Wei, 2018).

Application within the European Union

Following these and other international developments, the European Union (EU) has developed a Just Transition approach that is closely intertwined with its *Green Deal activities* and the aim to become carbon neutral. JT thereby provides a normative basis for economic development which intends to “*make the EU's economy sustainable [...] by turning climate and environmental challenges into opportunities and making the **transition just and inclusive for all***” (EC, 2019). The European Commission (EC) therefore supports fossil fuel regions¹ and has set-up the Coal Regions in Transition Secretariat² to assist the most affected regions in adjusting their local economies, energy sectors and jobs-oriented initiatives so that ‘no one is left behind’. Further, a Just Transition Platform³ at EU level was established to support regions, industries and countries ensuring that policy and investment initiatives alleviate the economic, societal and environmental costs of transition to a climate-neutral economy. The Platform expanded the reach beyond extractive industries to encompass also carbon intensive industries (such as steel, cement, aluminium, fertilizers or paper production), assuming that these sectors, and the regions where they are concentrated, will be significantly impacted by the transition in terms of job losses and economic impact. The Just Transition Mechanism⁴ was established with the aim of supporting necessary investments, including the Just Transition Fund that is available to selected regions.

Theoretical context and applicability to the WFRM context

At the core of the EU’s JT approach lies the idea that justice and equity must form an integral part of low-carbon transitions in order to facilitate a more “*profound transition that could transform the economic and political structures that reproduce and exacerbate inequalities and power asymmetries*” (UNRISD, 2018). JT can therefore be a vehicle for looking deeper into values and worldviews driving development processes.

From a general conceptual point of view, **different understandings of Just Transition** exist and translate into demands that range “*from a simple claim for jobs creation in the green economy, to a radical critique of capitalism*” (Barca, 2015). More recent conceptualisations suggest that JT encompasses three main dimensions (see figure below), namely **procedural** justice (does policy selection inclusively address stakeholder interests and input, either via institutional measures or ad hoc incorporation of views?), **restorative** justice (how does the policy address past or expected harms or wrongdoing?), and **distributional** justice (who should bear the costs and benefits?) (Figure 1).

¹ European Commission (2021) Green Deal: Coal and other carbon-intensive regions and the Commission launch the European Just Transition Platform. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/IP_20_1201

² https://ec.europa.eu/energy/topics/oil-gas-and-coal/eu-coal-regions/secretariat-technical-assistance-regions-transition-start_en

³ https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal/finance-and-green-deal/just-transition-mechanism/just-transition-platform_en

⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal/finance-and-green-deal/just-transition-mechanism_en

Figure 1: Just Transition concepts and its core components. Source: own figure, based on McCauley and Heffron (2018)

Presupposing that JT encompasses these three dimensions, it offers a wide area of application and allows for an understanding of the implications of transition processes more generally. This could include for example the analysis of a **wider range of economic sectors** and fields beyond climate mitigation. Simultaneously, the above detailed JT concept provides an angle about the **justice implications of transition processes** and potential measures that need to be taken to ensure they are perceived as just. This relates for example to the stakeholders that need to be involved (procedural justice) or the compensatory measures that could be useful to counteract negative effects of transition processes.

This is of particular importance since WFRM involves a broad range of stakeholders and sectors, all of which also undergoing mitigation related transitions. For example, holistic WFRM is interrelated with sectoral changes for example in agriculture and forestry, energy production related infrastructure systems and the construction sector, e.g. as it moves towards wood panel building⁵. In addition to these transitions, holistic WFRM faces a range of trade-offs for example between nature conservation and vegetation management. For instance, some climate actions such as the 3 Billion Trees Pledge⁶ initiative may influence future wildfire risk in those reforested areas since fire-prone environs are being extended across EU territories due to climate change (Hermoso et al., 2021).

The management of climate-related risks has so far been overlooked in JT conceptualisations. WFRM thereby offers the experimental grounds to apply JT to a new and complex setting from an academic and theoretical perspective. At the same time, Firelogue not only aims to test and adapt the applicability of JT in a new context. It also operationalises the concept to facilitate the discussion in five thematic working groups and throughout four thematic strands (see Annex 1). The aim is to understand how JT can be applied in the Green Deal context to guide multi-stakeholder processes and to determine the underlying drivers of disadvantaging certain stakeholders or uncovering synergies between them. Some potential conflicts and synergies are detailed in Annex I for thematic fields such as environment/ecology, infrastructure or insurance.

⁵ See for example Green Deal-bolstered New European Bauhaus strategy, also backed by the recent EU Forest Strategy: https://europa.eu/new-european-bauhaus/index_es

⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/environment/3-billion-trees_en

2. Introduction and definition of integrated wildfire risk management and the cross-sectoral and multi-stakeholder implications

2.1. Integrating multi-aspects of (wild)fire (risk) management

The need for integrated approaches to disaster risk management is well stated in the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015–2030 (UNDRR, 2015), which aims to:

*“Prevent new and reduce existing disaster risk through the implementation of **integrated and inclusive** economic, structural, legal, social, health, cultural, educational, environmental, technological, political and institutional measures that **prevent** and reduce hazard exposure and vulnerability to disaster, increase **preparedness for response and recovery**, and thus strengthen **resilience**”*

This integrated approach across dimensions (i.e., social, economic, etc.) comprises the inclusion of disaster risk reduction (DRR) as well into other cross-sectoral policies as it is mentioned in Priority 3 (see Figure 2):

“(n) To strengthen the sustainable use and management of ecosystems and implement integrated environmental and natural resource management approaches that incorporate disaster risk reduction;

“(q) To promote and integrate disaster risk management approaches throughout the tourism industry, given the often heavy reliance on tourism as a key economic driver.”

Priority 1. Understanding disaster risk	Priority 2. Strengthening disaster risk governance to manage disaster risk	Priority 3. Investing in disaster risk reduction for resilience	Priority 4. Enhancing disaster preparedness for effective response and to “Build Back Better” in recovery, rehabilitation and reconstruction
Disaster risk management should be based on an understanding of disaster risk in all its dimensions of vulnerability, capacity, exposure of persons and assets, hazard characteristics and the environment. Such knowledge can be used for risk assessment, prevention, mitigation, preparedness and response.	Disaster risk governance at the national, regional and global levels is very important for prevention, mitigation, preparedness, response, recovery, and rehabilitation. It fosters collaboration and partnership.	Public and private investment in disaster risk prevention and reduction through structural and non-structural measures are essential to enhance the economic, social, health and cultural resilience of persons, communities, countries and their assets, as well as the environment.	The growth of disaster risk means there is a need to strengthen disaster preparedness for response, take action in anticipation of events, and ensure capacities are in place for effective response and recovery at all levels. The recovery, rehabilitation and reconstruction phase is a critical opportunity to build back better, including through integrating disaster risk reduction into development measures.

Figure 2: The four priorities of Sendai Framework

In the case of WFRM understanding wildfires as “any unplanned or uncontrolled fire affecting natural, cultural, industrial and residential landscapes” (adapted from FAO, 2010, in Murray et al., 2021) a comprehensive and systemic approach becomes fundamental, since wildfires are highly human-influenced unlike the majority of the geological and hydro-meteorological hazards (for instance, ignition control and fuel distribution may influence the level of hazard in a planned way, and its potential impact to the values at risk). Wildfire occurrence and damage reflects “current and past

policy, planning and governance decisions that have created a context where fire ignition and spread occurs across the landscape” (IUFRO, 2018 in Murray et al., 2021).

Therefore, wildfires as a **socionatural hazard** in origin (“*in that they are associated with a combination of natural and anthropogenic factors, including environmental degradation and climate change*”)⁷ are in an evolving context of risk (UNEP, 2022), where physical (landscape modulation resulting from land-uses changes (LUC) and increasing fire-prone environments from climate change (CC)) and other sociocultural aspects of hazard, exposure and vulnerability (e.g., risk culture and awareness, see Table 1) interact.

Probably favoured by the complexity of wildfire phenomena, integrated management approaches have been adopted to respond to the so-called “living with fire” paradigm, considering not only damaging fires but also beneficial ones (Myers, 2006; Silva et al., 2010). Moreover, that integrated approach is also used to strategically frame WFRM within disaster risk management stages (i.e., prevention-preparedness-response-recovery, Table 1) (UNEP, 2020). In this regards, Table 2 summarizes some definitions used for **Integrated Fire Management**, that although they share many similarities, a unique understanding is still lacking and may be represented in different ways (Figure 3 and 4). Fundamentally, three main facets are considered when dealing with integrated approach:

- across risk dimensions, such as social, economic, cultural and ecological, etc, (e.g., Sendai framework’ aim, Silva et al., 2010),
- across DRM stages (e.g., UNEP, 2020) or/and,
- across sectoral policies that directly/indirectly influence risk creation/reduction (e.g., Priority 3 of Sendai framework, Plana et al., 2015)

which can be mixed in one figure (Faivre et al., 2018).

Fewer references exist for an **integrated WFRM** concept, which normally focusses on damaging fires (where the use of “good fire” (i.e., prescribed fires) to prevent “bad fires” (i.e., wildfires) are integrated) including the socio-ecological dimension of the so-called “*fire smart territories*” (Tedim et al., 2016).

Therefore, wildfire disaster risk⁸ reduction must deal with a changing context of hazard, exposures and vulnerabilities (HEV) where, **holistically**, policies and related stakeholders addressing fire ignition and spread risk, potential impact of damaging fires, safety emergency management in an increasing dangerous fire environment and recovery strategies to mitigate future risk and cascading multi-risk effects meet along the DRM stages.

In next Chapter 2.2, for the case of WFRM, how the different actions (and inactions) along DRM phases interact with the process of risk reduction (or creation) is discussed. These trade-offs across HEV risk factors and DRM phases offer a frame, as well, where to fit the corresponding role of stakeholders in

⁷ <https://www.undrr.org/terminology/hazard>

⁸ **Disaster risk:** The potential loss of life, injury, or destroyed or damaged assets which could occur to a system, society or a community in a specific period of time, determined probabilistically as a function of hazard, exposure, vulnerability and capacity.

Annotation: The definition of disaster risk reflects the concept of hazardous events and disasters as the outcome of continuously present conditions of risk. Disaster risk comprises different types of potential losses which are often difficult to quantify. Nevertheless, with knowledge of the prevailing hazards and the patterns of population and socioeconomic development, disaster risks can be assessed and mapped, in broad terms at least.

It is important to consider the social and economic contexts in which disaster risks occur and that people do not necessarily share the same perceptions of risk and their underlying risk factors. <https://www.undrr.org/terminology/disaster-risk>

terms of risk responsibility. Lastly, this comprehensive approach may serve to explore potential cross-links between WFRM and the JT approach and its distributional, procedural and restorative dimensions (Chapter 4).

Table 1: Definition of hazard, exposures and vulnerability risk components and phases of disaster risk management

Risk components	
<p>Hazard: A process, phenomenon or human activity that may cause loss of life, injury or other health impacts, property damage, social and economic disruption or environmental degradation.</p> <p>Exposure: The situation of people, infrastructure, housing, production capacities and other tangible human assets located in hazard-prone areas.</p> <p>Vulnerability: The conditions determined by physical, social, economic and environmental factors or processes which increase the susceptibility of an individual, a community, assets or systems to the impacts of hazards. Coping capacity* is the ability of people, organizations and systems, using available skills and resources, to manage adverse conditions, risk or disasters.</p>	
Disaster risk management phases	
<p>Prevention: activities and measures to avoid existing and new disaster risks.</p> <p>Preparedness: aims at building the needed capacities to efficiently manage emergencies and achieve orderly transitions from the response to a sustained recovery phase.</p> <p>Response: actions taken directly before, during or immediately after a disaster in order to save lives, reduce health impacts, ensure public safety and meet the basic subsistence needs of the people affected.</p> <p>Recovery**: the restoring or improving of livelihoods and health, as well as economic, physical, social, cultural and environmental assets, systems and activities, of a disaster-affected community or society, aligning with the principles of sustainable development and “build back better”, to avoid or reduce future disaster risk.</p>	

Source: UNDRR <https://www.undrr.org/terminology/> *Coping capacity is often linked to Vulnerability/ **Restoration, or Restoration and adaptation is also commonly named for this stage.

Table 2: Definitions of Integrated Fire Management

Myers, 2006	<p>IFM is an approach to addressing the problems and issues posed by both damaging and beneficial fires within the context of the natural environments and socio-economic systems in which they occur, by evaluating and balancing the relative risks posed by fire with the beneficial or necessary ecological and economic roles that it may play in a given conservation area, landscape or region.</p> <p>IFM framework incorporates the ecological, socio-economic and technical aspects of fire in a holistic fashion, (1) to address the social and conservation problems and issues that result from the burning of vegetation, and (2) to meet the goal of sustainable ecosystems and human livelihoods in fire-prone environments.</p> <p>IFM is not a new term, as a quick internet search will attest. It has been previously used to narrowly define the integration of fire suppression actions such as early warning, detection, initial attack and recovery. The term “Integrated Fire Management” has also been used to describe fire management approaches in less developed regions involving communities, rural land users, government agencies and non-governmental organizations (FAO 2003). In the latter case, it has at times been inappropriately synonymous with Community-based Fire Management (Goldammer et al. 2002) (...). The meaning of IFM in this paper is the integration of science and society with fire management technologies at multiple levels. It implies a holistic or seamlessly-woven comprehensive approach to address fire issues that considers biological, environmental, cultural, social, economic and political interactions (Kaufmann et al. 2003). The concepts can be applied to all regions of the world irrespective of development status.</p>
Silva et al., 2010	<p>IFM: A concept for planning and operational systems that include social, economic, cultural and ecological evaluations with the objective of minimizing the damage and maximizing the benefits of fire. These systems include a combination of prevention and suppression strategies and techniques that integrate the use of technical fires and regulate traditional burning.</p>
FYNBOSFIRE, 2016	<p>IFM incorporates different fire management activities in a strategic framework to reduce the overall impact of unwanted wildfire damage and promote the beneficial use of fire. It is a series of actions that includes fire awareness activities, fire prevention activities, prescribed burning, resource sharing and co-ordination, fire detection, fire suppression, fire damage rehabilitation and research at local, provincial and national levels in order to create a sustainable and well-balanced environment, reduce unwanted wildfire damage, and promote the beneficial use of fire.</p>
Faivre et al., 2018	<p>IFM builds upon a combination of prevention and suppression strategies stemming from social, economic, cultural and ecological evaluations. Beyond the sole consideration of fire prevention and fire suppression, IFM links the four steps of emergency crisis management, i.e., mitigation, preparedness, response and recovery.</p> <p>The challenge is to develop integrated solutions which take into account the objectives of forestry, urban and rural development, agricultural, climate and energy policies to ensure that wildfires are managed in such a way that the safety of people and housing, economic growth and ecosystem services are maintained or increased</p>
UNEP 2022	<p>While fire is a natural ecological process, changes to our climate and land-use are contributing to more wildfires. Dealing effectively with the increase in wildfires requires policies and incentives that promote IFM approaches. Achieving and sustaining adaptive land and fire management requires a well-designed and balanced combination of policies, a clear legal framework, and incentives that encourage appropriate land and fire use. These approaches maintain and restore healthy ecosystems while meeting the social, economic, and health needs of human populations.</p> <p>Integrated wildfire* management consists of five interlinked and often overlapping phases: review and analysis, risk reduction, readiness, response, and recovery. Review and analysis and risk reduction generally take place prior to the onset of the fire season and are focused on preventing avoidable outbreaks (e.g., ensuring fire ban compliance, improving understanding of arsonist behaviour, power line maintenance, and general fire safety awareness) ensuring communities and authorities are aware of the risk of wildfire and have thought about what needs to be done in the event of a wildfire. Readiness focuses on the actions to be carried out during the fire season before a wildfire breaks out and includes preparing properties, early detection of outbreaks, and having suppression resources on standby. Response includes the actions undertaken during a wildfire and focuses on reducing the potential impact of the wildfire through active suppression or relocating communities or assets under threat. Recovery (the planning for which should begin during the response phase) focuses on those actions to minimise disruption to the community, repairing infrastructure and restoring landscapes.</p> <p><i>*or fire in the same document</i></p>

INTEGRATED FIRE MANAGEMENT

Figure 3: Components of IFM in FYNBOSFIRE (2016)

Figure 4: Policy challenges and Policy recommendations across the IFM (Favre et al., 2018)

2.2. Trade-offs across risk components and disaster risk management stages along wildfire risk creation/reduction process

Risk mitigation measures are distributed along all stages of the DRM stages (from prevention to recovery) where different public and private stakeholders are involved and participate in the process of risk creation or reduction that influences hazards, exposures and vulnerabilities. Subsequently, actions (and inactions) of stakeholders, policies, initiatives, etc., may impact on risk creation and reduction process.

In this regards, different categories of stakeholders may be defined (IUFRO, 2018): Stakeholders that **create the present risk** (i.e., land use activities and attitudes and actions of people at risk) and **future risk** (such as urban expansion, governance, changes in lifestyle or values, vegetation interactions, possibly emergency management trends and climate change), and those **dealing with** the results of the activities that create **the risk** (e.g., fire and emergency services, insurers, forest and land managers or exposed population and sectors). In terms of stakeholders engagement and dialogue, two specific roles specifically related to distributional, procedural and restorative justice dimensions may be included:

- those actors who are **“providing” risk mitigation** (e.g., forest owners managing forests and avoiding high intensity fire behaviours) and,
- those who are **“benefiting” from risk mitigation** (e.g., homeowners and touristic resorts protected or less vulnerable to wildfire impact).

That trade-off across actions creating/deconstructing risk may be easily expressed through risk components interdependence, since the higher the **hazard** the greater the **exposure**, and increased efforts to decrease **vulnerability** (including **coping capacity**) are needed. Consequently, by reducing H, there is less E, and less V reduction is needed. On the contrary, those inactions in reducing the hazard are, somehow, shifting the risk mitigation to the management of exposures, and so on.

Along this process of risk creation and reduction and trade-offs among actions/inactions, different moral, economic, legal or procedural implications (and gaps) in terms of **risk responsibility** may appear. Raike and McBean (2016) for example discuss how the lack of standards in emergency management legislation expose private landowners to greater vulnerability to disasters and the liability attached. According to the authors, for instance, *“It is essential that those responsible for proactive/preventative planning for disasters work from a standard playbook, one which sets minimum safeguards for the public. Absent of clear and fulsome compensation guidelines, private landowners will bear an unfair and disproportionate financial risk”*. Hazard-resistant building codes (FEMA, 2020), standardized and official risk maps limiting or conditioning urban developments, or evacuation and confinement agreed protocols adjusted to the level of preparedness of the infrastructures are some examples of this cross-links between risk reduction, coping capacity and final risk assumed by different stakeholders.

This HEV sequence is particularly relevant in the case of wildfires, assuming biomass fuel as one of the main risk drivers of hazard. Therefore, hazardous high-fuel load landscapes propagating high intensity fires that overwhelm suppression capacity and impact on exposed elements may be modified. At exposure level, a proper planning adapted to fire risk should avoid building houses into wooded lands. Addressing this underlying risk driver will reduce subsequent disaster risk. If we cannot reduce the severity of natural hazards, neither the exposures, the main opportunity for reducing risk lies in

reducing vulnerability (e.g., promoting fire-resistant building codes or actions that can make wildfire evacuation quicker, easier and safer).

In consequence, the final risk results from the combination of actions increasing/reducing HEV factors. High levels of HEV may collapse the system and increase the socially assumed **residual risk**⁹ threshold. On that sense, residual risk may become a critical factor in the case of the so-called extreme wildfire events (EWE) (Tedim, 2018), capable to jeopardize DRR strategies not planned neither adapted to those “extremes”.

Trade-offs across risk factors and actions/inactions can also be expressed through **DRM stages**. **Prevention** actions may act reducing the H (reducing fuels at landscape level) and E and V (integrating wildfire risk into urban and spatial planning, limiting and guiding urban developments). In terms of **preparedness**, coping capacity (V) may be reinforced by Civil Protection (CP) protocols for safety confinement or evacuation. Access control to forest massifs during high fire risk periods aims at H (ignition risk) and E (limiting the presence of visitors which will constrain suppression capacity as well) reduction. Moreover, coping capacities are increased at local level (no need to safe people in case of fire) and regional level (less probability of simultaneous fire events). At the **response** level, the more trained, efficient, and equipped the Fire Service is, the greater its coping capacity. Within the **recovery** stage, insurances and compensation mechanisms will reduce the V, and build back better¹⁰ may reduce future HEVs.

Therefore, in a high HEV context, response is offering a limited capacity to reduce the risk, since it is acting on the “accumulated” risk from the previous stages. This helps to understand the far-reaching connection among risk factors and mitigation measures within the DRM cycle, in a similar sequence as in the case of HEV: the more prevention actions are adopted, the fewer the preparedness and response efforts are needed, and lower recovery impacts may be expected. The assumption (or lack thereof) of risk reduction measures will influence how to manage the emergency and the final impact of the event on citizens, infrastructures, and the landscape ecosystem services (residual risk).

Indeed, there is not just one DRR pathway, and how to manage wildfire risk can be balanced according to the level (and frequency) of H, to the own coping capacity and to the values at risk to be protected. Previous EWEs illustrate the collapse of the “standard” WFRM system. Consequently, in order to face this “rare”, “unprecedented” or “more frequent” events, additional prevention, preparedness and recovery actions to reduce HEV factors must be needed. Alternatively, DRR strategy could be adjusted to different risk scenarios, for instance, adopting a defensive strategy with specific CP protocols and strong build back better programs to face EWE, but investing in less flammable landscape as the most cost-efficient option when dealing with “common” fires.

In this respect, targeted residual risk could be pre-defined (and agreed upon) at a multi-stakeholder level (i.e., those creating and managing risk, and between providers and beneficiaries of mitigation), adapting DRR strategies to the specific risk threshold socially agreed. Across this dialogue with stakeholders, trade-offs among risk reduction actions/inactions and the corresponding risk shifting

⁹ **Residual risk** is the disaster risk that remains even when effective disaster risk reduction measures are in place, and for which emergency response and recovery capacities must be maintained. The presence of residual risk implies a continuing need to develop and support effective capacities for emergency services, preparedness, response and recovery, together with socioeconomic policies such as safety nets and risk transfer mechanisms, as part of a holistic approach. <https://www.undrr.org/terminology/disaster-risk>

¹⁰ **Build back better**: The use of the recovery, rehabilitation and reconstruction phases after a disaster to increase the resilience of nations and communities through integrating disaster risk reduction measures into the restoration of physical infrastructure and societal systems, and into the revitalization of livelihoods, economies and the environment. <https://www.undrr.org/terminology/build-back-better>

implications within DRM stages could be addressed. Moreover, stakeholders' role (in terms of responsibility and/or contribution) in the risk creation but also reduction process could be defined, favouring integrated risk-sharing approaches (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Comprehensive frame to guide dialogue on trade-offs across creation and reduction of risk, the role stakeholders' and synergies and inconsistencies among sectoral policies

The increasing risk context due to vegetation changes, fire policy changes, or other effects of LUC & CC is stressing suppression-focused strategies, which is precisely when a better balance among HEV factors and DRM measures within integrated WFRM is needed. Stakeholders' engagement should help to articulate the corresponding roles and contributions from individuals and private and public bodies, in a more systemic, synergistic and policy-coherent frame, being aware of distributional, procedural and restorative justice dimensions.

2.3. A multi-agency and multi-stakeholder approach to become integrated

At the institutional level, risk reduction actions are distributed across different agencies and the corresponding competences along DRM stages (i.e., Forest Service for prevention and restoration or Civil Protection and Fire Service for preparedness and response, etc.). This multi-agency approach, when managing wildfire risk, is also deployed and featured at territorial scales, from the state to the regions (especially relevant in decentralized state models) up to local levels (the mayor, for instance, acts as an authority of Civil Protection). In terms of risk management, all those public bodies may be complemented with formal or informal collaborations of volunteers, farmers and foresters organised in civil forest defence associations or any other kind of volunteer platforms such as Virtual Operations Support Teams (VOST) groups.

In this sense, within the prevention phase it is useful to distinguish an active prevention – planned and implemented with main objective of reducing wildfire ignition or spread capacity (i.e., control of ignitions, fuel-breaks and perimeter strips, etc.) – and the passive prevention – carried out by

agroforestry activities which influences wildfire risk through fuel reduction at landscape level, although risk reduction is not its main objective.

In this regard, since high-fuel loads landscapes become a hazard factor, win-win strategies may be adopted by the promotion of fire-resistant landscapes through a bio-based economy (see Chapter 4.1). Wildfire prevention resulting from less flammable landscapes able to “protect” the values at risk may be seen as an ecosystem service (regulation) which is provided by foresters and farmers. In terms of policies and financial tools, this approach may be aligned within the implementation of payment for ecosystem services under the scope of nature-based solutions¹¹ (NBSs) for disaster risk reduction (UNDRR, 2020a; Dumitru and Wendling, 2021). On that sense, potential stresses (Kramer et al., 2022), conflicts but also synergies among wildfire prevention and other ecosystem services such as biodiversity conservation or water provision should be balanced and properly addressed within risk reduction strategies.

Besides, that approach may be easily integrated within the narrative of the role of forest as a green infrastructure, for instance, towards the achievements of SDGs within the Urban Agendas. Therefore, focussing this “protection” ecosystem service provision, stakeholders benefiting from it may be consistently involved in the discussion around the WFRM.

¹¹ “Actions to protect, conserve, restore, sustainably use and manage natural or modified terrestrial, freshwater, coastal and marine ecosystems, which address social, economic and environmental challenges effectively and adaptively, while simultaneously providing human well-being, ecosystem services and resilience and biodiversity benefits.” Definition formally agreed by the United Nations Environment Assembly (UNEA), March 2, 2022

3. Impacts of climate change on wildfires patterns and risk management

Climate change is modifying natural hazard situations as they are known, increasing their intensity, frequency, and distribution (IPCC, 2021), while there is a high level of uncertainty about its specific impacts, overall, at regional and local level, compromising decision-making.

Regarding wildfires, most of the studies point toward an increase of fire intensity, frequency and areas affected due to increased drought, higher air temperatures, lower relative humidity, dryer lightning, and stronger winds; resulting in hotter, drier, and longer fire seasons (UNEP, 2022, Rossi et al., 2020, IUFRO, 2018).

Accordingly, fire prone conditions may increase both where wildfires previously occurred and in new regions that previously did not experienced wildfires. These new risk conditions posed by climate change may be exacerbated by socioecological changes occurring at the landscape level, leading to the expansion of fuels, such as agricultural abandonment, fire-suppression centred policies (so called fire-paradox), invasive species, forest plantations, etc., allowing the occurrence of EWE.

Those new (neither known nor pre-planned) risk scenarios may, therefore, increase societal residual risk. In this context, the potential role of cooperative and mutual insurance sector to reduce disaster losses (UNDRR, 2020b) may become more preponderant within WFRM strategies facing EWE to achieve resilient communities (Galbraith, 2017). In this regard, the need to become resilient to climate change impacts may has different implications and its more inclusive socio-ecological dimension (Nikinmaa et al., 2020) is which probably better reflect the multiple aspects associated to WFRM.

Consequently, new risk scenarios may modify HEV-DRM trade-offs, and they are known in all territories (traditional fire-prone and new risk areas), redefining stakeholders' roles and demands (which includes new communities at risk) that should be managed under justice principles.

4. Just Transition implications for stakeholder inclusion and relevance to wildfire risk management

4.1. Axis 1: How climate change, climate mitigation actions and related Just Transition may influence wildfire risk management and vice-versa

Climate actions, transition to resilient economies and communities and WFRM

Climate action is at the heart of the European Green Deal (EC, 2019). In this sense, the contribution of a global bioeconomy, based on the sustainable utilisation of renewable natural resources in the production of energy, products and services to face climate change challenges (Hetemäki et al., 2022) will play an increasing role. This new paradigm and its essential part of a forest-based circular bioeconomy is especially relevant in terms of WFRM, due to the influence of fuel loads distribution at the landscape level in wildfire outcomes. EU-level policies and measures addressing climate change mitigation policies such as an increased use of renewable energy (biomass) may, therefore, be aligned with wildfire risk reduction and be coherently framed within EU Bioeconomy Strategy (EC, 2018) in synergy with other harvested-wood products promoted by the EU Forest Strategy (EC, 2021a), while achieving EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change (EC, 2021b) targets.

In consequence, climate actions related to the consumption of forestry and agriculture products may be synergistically adopted with the WFRM. From a Civil Protection policy perspective, synergies may be established with sustainable forest management providing forests stand less vulnerable to crown fires able to “protect” citizens and infrastructures from high intensity fires (versus unmanaged hazardous forest), shifting risk mitigation from preparedness and response stages to prevention. WFRM may be aligned, therefore, with the “*promotion of nature-based solutions for adaptation*” and “*reducing climate-related risk*” according to the EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change, recognising (by policy and economic tools such as the eco-schemes foreseen in the Common Agriculture Policy) the provision of fire prevention ecosystem services offered by foresters and farmers.

In the same line, when the Climate-ADAPT platform states that “*new and existing buildings need to be assessed for resilience to current risks and future climate changes and planned or upgraded accordingly*”¹², it directly addresses the effective integration of WFR into urban and spatial planning (reducing exposures and vulnerabilities). This adaptation to climate change may be extended to strategic economic sectors such as tourism along the Mediterranean coastline for instance, which may suffer the impact of climate risk like EWE in the summer with thousands of people exposed (Lopes et al., 2021).

Other practical examples show the potential synergies between the use of prescribed fire by local communities to avoid greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) from wildfires intensively burnt, incentivised by local carbon credits market (Box 1).

¹² <https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/eu-adaptation-policy/sector-policies/buildings>

Box 1: Employment, culture preservation and environmental protection. Aboriginal landowners’ engagement in the carbon industry - ALFA organization, Australia

In the remote tropical savannas of northern Australia’s Arnhem Land, without customary land management due to land abandonment, wildfires burned intensely over thousands of square kilometres, with its consequent greenhouse gas emissions.

From this point, the Aboriginal landowners and a group of non-Indigenous scientists began a talk about the importance of having a “healthy country”, and the use of fire management as a key contributor. Aboriginal ranger groups refined their ability to manage fire across large landscapes and developed ways of emulating customary fire management using modern tools.

As managing fire on a large scale requires large financial capabilities, Arnhem Land Fire Abatement (ALFA) organisation was created by Aboriginal landowners to support their engagement in the carbon industry. They are currently developing 5 fire projects across an area of more than 80.000 km². The projects generate carbon credits through Federal Government legislation focused on carbon farming, which provides financial incentives to organisations and individuals to reduce their GHG. The ALFA-generated carbon credits represent an opportunity to offset the fire management works from Aboriginal people. Therefore, the organization facilitates a mechanism to go through a WFRM, green economies, reduction of GHG and employment.

Source: <https://www.alfant.com.au/about-us>

Fire-smart planning aimed at citizens, business and nature conservation (urban planning and agendas, tourist sector, green infrastructure, etc.) to increase their resilience (climate change adaptation) and defining self-responsibility boundaries of the exposed communities and sectors, is an essential part of the integrated WFRM approaches that may be aligned to a just transition in the transition away from high-carbon business models to a net-zero GHG economy.

Nevertheless, climate actions may also create inconsistencies in terms of WFRM. The deployment of renewable solar energy or wind turbines facilities in fire prone wooded lands may increase present and future wildfire risk if they are not planned considering the corresponding mitigation measures. Similarly, new wooded areas, established for energy purposes or biological conservation, can exacerbate wildfire hazard. Consequently, new risk management needs are shifted to those actors dealing with the results of the activities that create the risk (see Chapter 2), such as Fire Service and Civil Protection bodies.

Accordingly, how climate actions are planned and executed may influence globally WFRM. Based on the above-mentioned examples, the Figure 6 shows some potential interlinkages between the sequential trade-offs across HEV and DRM stages and JT dimensions.

Figure 6: Example of trade-offs across risk creation/reduction process and potential interlinkages with JT dimensions

Table 3 and 4 summarize several examples explored within the Firelogue consortium about the contributions and synergies between WFRM and climate change mitigation, and how a successful transition to net-zero emissions may contribute to promoting integrated WFRM. A consultation process was agreed offering to the entire consortium the opportunity to contribute using the online Miro Whiteboard tool where a set of questions was shared. Additionally, a specific workshop was conducted with the working group and thematic strands leaders to discuss those JT-WFRM interlinkages based on the same questions. Screenshots with the partners contributions are presented in Annex 2. In next tables results are grouped in main topics, linking them to Firelogue WGs scope.

Table 3: Examples of contributions and synergies between wildfire risk reduction and climate change mitigation, and relation with Firelogue working group scope

Main contributions and synergies associated with wildfire risk management to climate change mitigation identified by Firelogue participants	EN	SO	IN	IS	CP
<p><u>GHG emissions reduction</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fuel management actions to modify wildfire behaviour might reduce GHG emissions from forest fires (less fire intensity). - GHG emissions from forest fires strongly contribute to global GHG emissions. Any reduction of forest fires GHG emissions will have strong positive implications for climate change mitigation. 	X				
<p><u>Nature conservation</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conservation and preservation of biodiversity (<i>in a global sense; protecting landscapes from wildfire biodiversity is protected</i>). - Better consideration of the environment, its dynamics, and its disturbances by citizens. 	X	X			
<p><u>Improvement of carbon sink/stocks</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Forest management and fuel treatments to reduce wildfire risk might improve carbon sink/stocks and stock CO² in a saver way. 	X				
<p><u>Reinforcing public awareness on climate change – wildfire risk interlinkages</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improved wildfire risk perception from the general public needs to go hand in hand with increased public awareness in terms of climate change expected impacts. - An opportunity to better understand (human and natural) triggers for and impacts of distributional differences in longer term risks (<i>e.g., across sectors and future generations</i>). - WFRM and climate change mitigation require awareness of the complex interrelationships between people and landscapes. - Climate defines the fire regime (<i>related to frequency, intensity, etc.</i>) in a given geographic area by determining the typology and form of the vegetation (<i>in terms of biomass fuel</i>) in that area, as well as its susceptibility to fire (<i>e.g., vegetation recovery capacity in burnt areas</i>). Climate change can be thus determining for wildfire typology and severity. 	X	X	X		X
<p><u>Integrated and cost-efficient risk management</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Agrotourism contributes to local development in touristic areas and in parallel to effective fuel treatment for the elimination of mega-fires. - Integrated management of forest (<i>as a green infrastructure</i>) and city development. - Fuel management through use of fire (prescribed burning). 	X				X
<p><u>Potential inconsistencies</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How does afforestation in line with national Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use (AFOLU) mitigation targets influence wildfire risk in the long term? Afforested areas may be close to vulnerable assets & infrastructure. - Trade-off between public support for fire-impacted households (one option for financial risk management) as a disincentive to move away from increasing risk areas (adaptation). - Energy transition, a direct measure towards climate change mitigation may affect positively or negatively WFRM considering that new types of infrastructures will be operating, and others will shut down. 	X		X	X	X
<p><u>Others</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fire resistance housing. - Opportunity to rebuild with more climate adapted infrastructure. - Health impact of wildfire and climate change. 		X	X		

Working groups. **EN:** Environmental/Ecology, **SO:** Societal, **IN:** Infrastructures, **IS:** Insurances, **CP:** Civil Protection

Some comments have been added by the authors of the report (in italic) to help the understanding of the short text used in the Miro board.

Table 4: Examples of contributions and synergies between transition to net-zero emissions and wildfire risk, and relation with Firelogue working group scope

What would a successful transition to net-zero emissions contribute to promote an integrated WFRM?	EN	SO	IN	IS	CP
<p><u>Bioeconomy and nature-based solutions promotion</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CO² neutrality target, might stimulate sustainable forest derived products (also biomass fossil fuels substitution) that might require forest management and thus risk reduction. - Nature-based solutions and implementation of green technology. - A net-zero transition will require thinking about new livelihoods for those who will no longer be employed in high-emission industries. This could also comprise new agricultural livelihoods, such as shepherding, which would have an impact on wildfire risk reduction. 	X				
<p><u>Sustainable development</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Intergenerational trade-offs sustainable development goals. - Substantial changes in agricultural and forestry practices will be needed for a successful net zero. transition. WFRM should be considered when implementing the required changes in order to develop synergies and prevent trade-offs. 	X	X			
<p><u>Potential inconsistencies</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A counter to this question: many wildfires are started by downed electrical lines, yet the move to net-zero requires increases in electrical infrastructure. - Renewable energy installations are more distributed and in remote areas, fire can be triggered more easily – protection measures need to be taken + awareness of local communities must be increased. - Massive RES upscaling will have impact on WFR and WFRM should be involved in Renewable Energy Source (RES) strategy development. 			X		X
<p><u>Others</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is research that N₂O (Nitrous oxide) changes soil composition, thus encouraging the growth of more flammable grasses. Net-zero could help reduce such fuel. - Both require a more systemic thinking. - Some of this depends on how the idea of net-zero is understood? Is it just carbon? Is it also N₂O? Or methane? The term is often used in a range of ways, inclusive and exclusive of these. 	X				
	X	X	X	X	X

Working groups. **EN:** Environmental/Ecology, **SO:** Societal, **IN:** Infrastructures, **IS:** Insurances, **CP:** Civil Protection

In sum, climate action (and a related just transition) as foreseen in the European Green Deal is offering a chance to promote the synergies and coherences across sectoral policies directly or indirectly related to WFRM. In this sense, a promising common framework where to embed integrated WFRM may be articulated by the combination of above-mentioned EU policies, together with the EU Biodiversity strategy for 2030 (EC, 2020a), Common Agricultural Policy¹³, Farm to fork Strategy (EC, 2020b) and those related to Civil Protection¹⁴, to name only a few. Stakeholders' engagement and dialogue should help to solve potential conflicts and inconsistencies in terms of land use, biodiversity conservation and risk shifting issues across policies and actions.

¹³ https://ec.europa.eu/info/food-farming-fisheries/key-policies/common-agricultural-policy/cap-glance_en

¹⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/echo/what/civil-protection/eu-civil-protection-mechanism_en

Impacts of climate change in WFRM and potential implications in Just Transition dimensions

According to Chapter 3, the changing and increasing wildfire risk context posed, among others, by climate change may challenge WFRM at different dimensions (technology and procedures, policies, community engagement and risk culture, etc.). Table 5 shows some potential impacts on risk management within the DRM stages. Some of those impacts may be related to the three dimensions of just transition, for instance:

- **Distributional justice (cost and benefits):** In a climate change context with an increasing need of risk mitigation that may lead to the collapse of public service, are those private and business sectors benefiting from fire prevention participating in financing WFRM?
- **Procedural justice (stakeholder engagement):** How new fire communities along the extended fire-prone territories resulting from climate change are being involved within WFRM?
- **Restorative justice (compensatory past or expected harms):** are policies addressing present but also future risk? Are new wildfire risk scenarios well known enough?

All those challenges posed by climate change should be mapped and considered when dialoguing with stakeholders not only in terms of facing current situation but also for being able to adapt to future risks.

Table 5: Examples of climate change impacts on wildfire risk management and interlinkages with Just Transition dimensions

DRM	Climate change impacts on risk management	D	P	R
Prevention	- Need of re-analysis and updating planning tools to increasing and/or unprecedented risks (and multi-risk) scenarios.			X
	- Limits of modelling increasing and/or unprecedented risk scenarios.			X
	- Need of developing a “culture of prevention” in new fire-prone areas to compensate suppression-centred policies that motivate a fire paradox ¹⁵ .	X	X	X
	- Increase the fire-prone areas and risk of funding collapse “to protect all”.	X		X
	- Need of engagement of actors and stakeholders in new fire-prone areas.		X	
	- Need of reinforcing collaborative approaches to face increased wildfire risk scenarios (that cannot be protected anymore from only public services).		X	X
	- Increasing restriction of activities and legal requirements in fire-prone areas.	X		X
	- Challenges for societal acceptance of “living with wildfires”		X	X
Preparedness	- Adapt civil protection protocols to extreme events and new multi-risk situations meeting different levels of expertise and competences (e.g., wildfires jeopardizing forest protection functions in mountain areas).		X	
	- Adapt early-warning systems to increased potential of damaging wildfires to impact on exposed population, buildings and roads (e.g., international tourist and resorts).			X
	- Lack of experience and adapted drills to extreme events			X
Response	- Ensuring exposed population, fire-fighters and emergency bodies safety in case of extreme events.			X
	- Simultaneous and/or more severe and/or longer wildfire events.	X		
	- Collapse or malfunction of defensive systems (fuel breaks, defensive irrigation in wildland urban interface, etc.).	X		
	- Face unprecedented events, adding complexity to emergency management and stressing the system.	X		
	- New fire prone areas with professionals without previous experience, neither adapted equipment and protocols to deal with wildfires.		X	X
	- Risk of collapse and frustration of emergency services			X
Recovery	- Increase of residual risk and disruption to communities due to “extreme” and/or unprecedented damaging wildfire events.	X	X	X
	- Potential irreversible effects in sensitive ecosystems to high (or low)-intensity or recurrent wildfires (desertification, gaps on species adaptation to unprecedented wildfire regimes in traditional and new fire-prone areas, etc.).	X		X
	- Cascading effects in ecosystem services (biodiversity conservation, water provision, etc.).	X		X
	- Impact to the insurance sector.	X		
	- Resistance to recovery measures (e.g., promotion of new tree species) adapted to new conditions (e.g., future drier conditions)		X	X

D: distributional, P: procedural, R: restorative

¹⁵ **Fire paradox** may be explained when “unintentionally, by focusing on short-term risks of wildfires” it “is predisposing forests to burn under the very worst conditions. Active fire suppression contributes to what is often referred to as the wildland fire paradox – the more we prevent fires in the short term, the worse wildfires become when they return” (Prichard et al., 2021). Therefore, paradoxically, using wildfire suppression to eliminate large and damaging wildfires ensures the inevitable occurrence of these fires. The term was mainly defined in North America, where natural fire regimes “burning during moderate weather conditions have largely ceased, commonly resulting in changes to vegetative composition, increasing fuel load, and broad-scale fuel continuity”. Then, “the historical fire patterns, burning under all conditions of fire spread, have now been replaced by fires that burn when fire suppression efforts fail as a result of high fire intensities and broad-scale fuel continuity. This shifts fire behavior characteristics to the most extreme in all vegetation zones and across the entire landscape” (Calkin et al., 2013).

4.2. Axis 2: Just Transition aspects within wildfire risk management

As discussed in Section 4.1 above, many sectors and issues beyond climate change mitigation have so far been neglected in the JT discourse. In contrast to existing conceptualizations, our definition of JT is situated within broader ideas of sustainability and resilience, which allows us to create an innovative framework of analysis through a transformational approach to considering distributional, procedural, and restorative justice. In Firelogue we will, for the first time, apply the JT concept in the context of wildfires and offer a possible interpretation of how to operationalize it for effective WFRM. We will focus on distributional, procedural and restorative/compensatory justice issues along the integrated WFRM cycle.

The questions suggested in the following can be understood as entry points for the Firelogue project team, in particular the WG leaders, (Figure 7) to understand and specify the manyfold JT implications (D: distributional, P: procedural, R: restorative) of wildfire impacts and of different WFRM measures along the four steps of the WFRM cycle (prevention, preparedness, response and restoration) and six human, physical and ecological elements that impact the risk management process (see Figure 4 above in Chapter 2) (Faivre et al. 2018).

Prevention: The key justice issues in this phase are centred around equal access to knowledge, resources and information needed to prevent wildfires, the distribution of costs and benefits of

wildfire prevention across society, and the inclusive consideration of stakeholder interests in the policy process of shifting focus from wildfire suppression to prevention.

- Human behaviour
 - Do policy processes shifting focus from suppression to prevention inclusively address stakeholder interests and input, in order to consider individual and local social and environmental contexts (P)?
 - Does everyone have equal access to resources and information (e.g., through public awareness campaigns) for prevention (D)?
 - How are costs and benefits distributed in the context of individual prevention (D)?
 - What may drive/hinder private (individual and business) level preventive actions (P, D)?
- Research & Innovation
 - Do R&I actions (e.g., emergency apps) sufficiently cover all relevant stakeholder interests (P, D)?
- Emergency management
 - Does a widespread use of a “shared responsibility” concept result in exclusion of those who aren’t or can’t be proactive in doing what is expected of them (D)?
- Ecosystems; socioeconomic; climate
 - How is (anthropogenic) climate change differently affecting individuals’ preventive capacities (D)?
 - Are lower socioeconomic strata more likely to live in poorer quality housing and higher hazard areas, leading to inequalities in exposure and vulnerability to wildfire (D)?
- Urban & land planning
 - Who should bear the costs and benefits of urban and land use planning and agroforestry development, in terms of increased or decreased wildfire risk (D)?
 - Are stakeholder inputs and interests inclusively addressed in urban & land use planning (P)?
- Biomass management
 - How can the (negative) impacts of biomass management and the impacts of fires be “compared” in terms of different impacts (losses, health, and mitigation) on different stakeholders (D)?
 - How does prevention through biomass management affect different functions of forests (i.e., economic use, recreational purpose, ecosystem services, etc) and thereby different stakeholder groups (D)?

Preparedness: The key justice issues in this phase are comprising the inclusive involvement of societal stakeholders in the development of preparedness tools, the distribution of the capacity to act across society, and the distribution of (knowledge on) residual wildfire risk despite prevention and preparedness activities.

- Human behaviour
 - Does everyone have equal access to information (e.g., evacuation plans) (D)?
 - Are citizens equally and adequately informed about potential residual risks? Do they know what this means (D)?
 - How is the capacity to act distributed across society (D)?
- Research & Innovation
 - With which audience in mind are preparedness tools developed (D, P)?
 - How are individuals involved in the development of preparedness tools (P)?
 - Are presumptions (internet access /literacy) well selected (D)?
- Emergency management
 - How are the costs and benefits of the current emergency management regime in terms of preparedness level distributed across society (D)?
- Ecosystems; socioeconomic; climate
 - How do we assess the adequate level between costs for preparedness and prevention programmes vs. costs for response activities (mainly machines, helicopters, etc.) (D)?
 - Preparedness can cost and take time: How are these resources distributed across society (D)?
 - What is the necessary degree of adjustment required from different members of society – who is affected by this change & to what extent (D)?
 - Is the opportunity cost of access restrictions for high fire risk days properly compensated (e.g., cancellation of tourist activities and reservations) (D)?
- Urban & land planning
 - Who should bear the costs and benefits of urban & land use planning, in terms of increased or decreased wildfire risk (D)?

Response: The key justice issues in this phase are related to the distribution of capacities to respond in case of emergency, the decision on where to put emphasize on in an emergency situation and where to accept residual risk, and the compensation for emerging residual damages.

- Human behaviour
 - Is knowledge on individual response measures readily and equally available to everyone (D)?
- Research & Innovation
 - Are stakeholder interests and inputs inclusively addressed in the design of response strategies (P)?
 - Are presumptions (internet access /literacy) well selected (D)?
- Emergency management
 - Universality of service; unequally distributed capacities of first responders and crises management; who pays in the end (national, state, local level; individual (voluntary and decent work)) (D)?
 - How are capacities to respond in case of emergency (dependence on public intervention vs. private emergency response capacity) distributed (D)?

- Who to decides where to put emphasis on in emergency situation and where to accept residual impacts? How are these decisions made (P)?
- How to communicate, that certain losses have to be accepted to avoid worse (P, D)?
- Ecosystems; socioeconomic; climate
 - How do we compensate if certain areas are “sacrificed” (C)?
 - How is (anthropogenic) climate change and socioeconomic development differently affecting individuals’ response capacities (D)?
- Biomass management
 - How are the positive/negative effects of a certain biomass management regime on the response phase distributed across society (D)?

Restoration and Adaptation: The key justice issues in this face comprise the distribution of benefits and costs of adaptation measures, the potential of individual adaptation action causing maladaptive outcomes at a societal level, the distribution of adaptive capacities across societies, and the role of insurance as a solidarity mechanism to provide restorative support.

- Human behaviour
 - Are stakeholder interests and inputs, as well as diverse adaptive capacities inclusively considered when designing policies to address past (restoration) and future (adaptation) harms (P, D)?
 - Do individual actions and incentives coincide and run the risk of causing mal-adaptive outcomes from a societal point of view (also accounting for intergenerational consequences) (D)?
 - What recovery strategies will be considered just and by whom (P, D)?
- Emergency management
 - Accessibility: provision of technical assistance for homeowners and private forest owners (D).
- Ecosystems; socioeconomic; climate
 - Accessibility of restorative support (insurance or aid) is an issue for many groups, especially “hard to reach” groups. These can include the undocumented (immigrants). There have been major disputes over how such groups should be treated. In parts of the US some groups have no legal right to emergency support. Similarly in Australia (D, C).
 - Are there public support measures in place, such as a disaster or adaptation fund (C)?
 - If yes, does everyone have equal access (D, C)?
 - Who is affected by the costs and benefits of nature-based solutions and are stakeholder concerns inclusively considered when designing and implementing NBSs (D, P)?
 - How are monetary and non-monetary adaptation efforts distributed (and how can we make sure to capture them sufficiently) (D)?

- Issue of insurance accessibility; and livelihood security for different socioeconomic groups (D, C).
- How are residual risks driven by climate change distributed across society (D)?
- How do socioeconomic drivers determine the distribution of residual impacts (D)?
- Urban & land planning
 - Post-impact changes or strict application of planning and building law can prevent people from rebuilding, exclude them from livelihoods, and devalue major assets (D).
 - Who should bear the costs and benefits of urban & land use planning, in terms of residual wildfire risk (D)?
 - Trade-offs between regulation/re-zoning and residual damage (D)?
 - How is past or expected harm included in adapting current urban & land use planning (D)?
 - How can Build-back-better be incentivised/enabled for everyone (D, P)?
 - What urban planning strategies should be incentivised to ensure a just recovery process? (P)
- Biomass management
 - How is the distribution of past or expected harm from wildfires considered in adapting a prevailing biomass management regime (D)?
 - How are the residual impacts, driven by a certain biomass management regime, distributed across society (D)?

The above listed questions have been collected by the project team at the start of the project, providing a broad overview of potential justice aspects that could emerge in the working group workshops. Not all of these questions will eventually be addressed in the course of the Firelogue project, but they should sensitize WG leaders to JT aspects in the context of WFRM. Moreover, some of these questions have been addressed in the risk management – not necessarily wildfire – literature to some extent, while others have not received attention so far.

5. Conclusions

Although the Just Transition concept is framed originally within the transition away from high-carbon business models to a net-zero greenhouse gas emissions economy, this report has identified consistent cross-links between wildfire risk management and the Just Transition approach.

On one side, WFRM-JT interlinkage may be defined under the scope of climate change mitigation and adaptation, and on balancing emission reduction activities under which JT concept is developed, by the synergies between:

- Wildfire risk reduction and GHG emission reduction.
- The increase of carbon sinks/stocks by forest cover conservation and a nature-based circular bioeconomy linked to biomass fuel management, offering new green job opportunities.
- The recognition of wildfire risk reduction actions as an ecosystem service, provisioned to adapting communities, infrastructures and business to climate related risks through nature-based solutions based on sustainable forestry and farming.
- The integration of present and future wildfire risk into the promotion of JT mechanism at EU level, in the development of renewable energies sector or within other climate actions, integrating the corresponding risk mitigation measures.

On the other hand, focusing on the effect of risk reduction measures from a justice perspective, JT thereby facilitates the outcome-oriented view of measures taken and relate them to compensation discussions. Conceptually, justice dimensions arise within the trade-offs established across actions and inactions influencing hazards, exposures and vulnerabilities or the interactions among DRM (from prevention to recovery). By tracing the risk creation/reduction process, the corresponding role of stakeholders (in terms of responsibility and contributions) may be addressed. From a justice perspective, inconsistencies and inequalities resulting from the lack of mechanisms to compensate the risk shifting across HEV risk factors and DRM stages may serve to guide the dialogue with stakeholders towards an integrated WFRM.

Based on the above, the report discusses how limiting disfunctions and promoting synergies across HEV-DRM trade-offs may support integrated wildfire risk reduction strategies, for instance, valuing the contribution of rural development that provides less flammable and hazardous landscapes as a tool for Civil Protection. In a similar way, those activities creating new exposures should be aware of managing the corresponding vulnerability reduction. On the contrary, those gaps on the initial sequence of risk creation are shifted to the final stages of disaster management and to those actors in charge of managing the risk.

In this regard, the changing risk context due to land-use changes and the climate change may re-define the role and participation of public and private stakeholders, and new risk responsibilities may appear. Moreover, extreme wildfire events or new fire-prone conditions may increase residual risk far from the thresholds socially and economically assumed by current DRR strategies.

Therefore, justice dimensions can then be interpreted within integrated WFRM principles, offering a consistent conceptual approach under which to frame risk reduction strategies across all related sectoral policies and stakeholders, in a coherent and systemic way.

On that sense, our reflection on JT aspects in the context of WFRM has resulted in a comprehensive list of salient questions in the domains of distributional, restorative and procedural justice. We have been able to identify issues of justice for each step in the wildfire risk management cycle and in even more detail for human, physical and ecological elements that impact the risk management process.

All these issues need to be addressed in order to establish WFRM approaches that are perceived as fair by relevant stakeholders, thereby limiting potential conflicts and increasing political feasibility. Within Firelogue we will now build on this initial assessment of potential justice issues to proactively address potential conflicts and synergies in the WFRM context. In particular, in setting up the working groups and identifying topics for the workshops, WG leaders will make sure to bring to the fore and explicitly address the often times implicit justice considerations along the WFRM cycle. With this deliverable we have laid the basis for the workshop design around a Firelogue-JT approach.

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Annex 1. Firelogue sectoral working groups and horizontal thematic strands

Working groups scope and thematic strands justification according to Firelogue project description.

Working groups scope	
Ecology/ Environment	A better understanding of ecosystems' response to changing fire-prone conditions and the influence of cross-sectoral policies to landscape modulation are two main pillars of the environmental dimension of WFRM. Novel knowledge and innovation actions should help managers in the current and future context of global change (i.e., considering climate change projections and the expected impacts of land use changes) to adapt and manage fire resilient landscapes across EU in a collaborative and cost-efficient manner. At forest stand level, for instance, in depth analysis of fuel management options to provide forest structures resistant to wildfires become imperative, maximizing synergies among sectoral policies such as bioeconomy or biodiversity conservation and protecting both not only forest but also society against high intensity fires.
Societal	Citizen engagement is key to successful WFRM during all phases of WFRM. It is linked for example with the designation of building areas and codes as well as the cleaning of vegetation on properties which also includes risk awareness and the adaptation of individual behaviour based on official guidance. However, it also links with precautionary measures during times of high risk as well as response measures in case of fire, relating for example to voluntary firefighting or the (support of) evacuations.
Infrastructure	Recent publications of the JRC ¹⁶ stressed interrelations between wildfires and industrial facilities and request policy-makers to develop multi-stakeholder activities to promote wildfire safety. Industrial operators are called to hold regular exchanges with local forest owners and land use planners. It is thereby important to stress that a mutual cause-effect relationship (including the potential for cascading effects) exists. For example, a frequent source of ignitions are arcing power lines. Similarly, infrastructures such as roads play a crucial role as evacuation routes. Overall, the interplay between wildfires and infrastructure can have crucial implications for training and operational procedures of responders, particularly if infrastructures are privately owned.
Insurance	The Sendai Framework has identified “ insurance, risk-sharing and retention and financial protection [...] for both public and private investment in order to reduce the financial impact of disasters on Governments and societies” as an important measure to manage disaster risk. This WG will discuss in detail the potential design and implementation of different insurance mechanisms (market-based, public-private arrangements, subsidized schemes, regional insurance pools, micro insurance) and assess their effectiveness in reducing financial impacts of wildfire risks in an equitable way. In particular, we will focus on potential interventions that can make insurance more affordable.
Civil Protection	Detection and response are central to managing wildfires. While new approaches and technologies may carry enormous potential in supporting response, they also bring along new challenges – e.g. when thinking about the deployment of unmanned vehicles. In addition, the financing of (new) response technologies vs. investments into forest management and prevention measures and the benefits for the various involved actors will play a role. At the same time, new and emerging approaches to assessing wildfire danger and risk and their implications as well new and existing SOPs will be discussed.
Thematic strands justification	
Socio-Economic Aspects	In the Western Mediterranean region of Europe, fuel loads are now greater than ever before due to rural abandonment and depopulation resulting from the decline in rural economies. ⁴² This exemplarily shows how WFRM is linked with socio-economic aspects that would have to be addressed in order to holistically address the risk. Consequently, this strand will review economic WFRM measures including for example taxation strategies and economic and business-related activities linked with agriculture and forestry. In addition, it will also conceptually contribute to an impact assessment of WFRM measures going beyond classical cost-benefit analysis, trying to integrate and quantify non-economic side-effects.

¹⁶ Kern et al. (2020): Wildfires Triggering Natech Events, JRC Science for Policy Report, available via: <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC121315>

Climate Change Mitigation and Adaptation	Surfaces burnt can no longer absorb CO² emissions and reduce the potential of carbon sinks to counter climate change. At the same time, prescribed burnings are a measure to reduce wildfire risk. Different tree species and forestry practices (changes in species) thereby determine the carbon sink potential ¹⁷ as well as wildfire risk . Consequently, different aspects have to be considered when designing mitigation and adaptation strategies which will be considered under this strand.
Technologies	A range of technologies is under development to facilitate WFRM. Among others, IAs will develop more advanced techniques, models , solutions and capabilities for preventing, predicting, monitoring and fighting wildfires , and mitigating their impact, including better and advanced technologies, equipment and decision support systems for first responders. However, some of them (i.e. modelling) can be subject to uncertainties that need to be put into context or bind several sectors together , for example when developing new risk transfer solutions also relating to cascading effects of infrastructure failure. Similarly, technologies used in wildfire response such as crowd-sourcing or other technology-based civil protection-citizen interaction linked for example with early-warning or evacuation management will be screened. Overall, this strand is closely linked with task 1.4 and will provide input to the WGs in terms of relevant new technological developments.
Earth Observation	Earth observation plays an important role in land-management and WFRM respectively. There is a range of solutions to facilitate WFRM such as the Copernicus Emergency Management System (EMS) or the Copernicus Land Service for monitoring changes in Land Cover/Land Use and providing Burnt Area Maps . The IAs will be working on further enhancing these services in terms of integrating new data (socioeconomic and environmental information on wildfire causes and impacts) and their use (access to official fire danger index rating and warnings). These developments will have different impacts (and also require input) from different sectors. This strand will hence link the working groups with the most recent EO developments .

¹⁷ For example Kirby & Potvin (2007): Variation in carbon storage among tree species: Implications for the management of a small-scale carbon sink project, in: Forest Ecology and Management, 246, 2–3, 208-221.

Annex 2. Firelogue partners contributions to WFRM, CC mitigation and Just Transition linkages

Next images are taken from the Miro board and show the contributions from Firelogue partners to the consultation process conducted online and in a workshop with working group and thematic strands leaders to discuss JT-WFRM interlinkages, based on set of questions:

What would a successful transition to net-zero emissions contribute to promote an integrated WFRM?

Could you flag examples where justice aspects are considered in WFRM measures even though they might not be mentioned under the Just Transition concept?

Which aspects of justice would holistic WFRM strategies have to address better?

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